

Design for policy in data for policy practices.

Exploring potential convergences for policy innovation.

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Abstract

This position paper recognises and investigates a gap between two fields of research and practice dealing with innovation in public policy: *data for policy* and *design for policy*. These fields act within government and the public sector, but with a different focus.

On the one hand, *data for policy* deals with the use of non-traditional digital data sources for policy-making (as administrative or citizens-generated data) and emergent organisational practices connected to these data (e.g., data collaboratives). On the other hand, *design for policy* inquiries the adoption of design approaches, methods and tools in policy-making and public services development. The difference in focus explains the current gap between the two fields and implies different approaches toward policy innovation.

This paper advances an argument in favour of explicitly and systematically connecting these fields. To do so, I propose three areas of convergences by looking at experiences in the *data for policy* field. In these areas, I look at the value of this integration through the lens of policy innovation, intended as *innovative ways of learning about policy-related matters that can influence the design of policies*. The perspective offered is directed to scholars and practitioners in both fields and hopes to sparkle a fruitful discussion on innovative policy epistemologies needed to address the contemporary complexity of policy problems. In the paper, I first contextualise my reasoning line by reviewing the concept of public sector innovation (PSI). Then I consider different disciplinary perspectives about one particular subset of PSI: *policy innovation*. Starting from these authors, I propose to see policy innovation as innovative ways of learning about policy-related matters that can influence the design of policies. I hypothesise three potential areas of convergence between *data for policy* and *design for policy* by holding this perspective. To support them, I will draw on illustrative examples found through a systematic review of

articles published in the past editions of the *Data for Policy* Conference.

Keywords – design for policy, policy design, policy epistemology, experimental policymaking

Introduction

Many public servants, policy scholars and government pundits may roll their eyes when hearing someone talking — once again — about innovation in the public sector. As fashionable as unclear, the concept of innovation might seem just a recurring fad by those who knows well the rigidity of the public sector's structures. Nonetheless, some conceptual ambiguity might as well be fruitful. Jenson (2015) noted that *quasi-concepts* (e.g., social cohesion or social innovation) largely populate the political and policy discourses. A certain degree of indefiniteness grants these concepts the capacity of gathering diverse policy actors around timely issues, enacting new positive practices and experimentations. Whether or not we consider it a quasi-concept, innovation in government and public sector (often referred to as *public sector innovation* or *public innovation*) appears to have fuelled unseen practices and originated new fields. The two fields considered in this article seem to be the case: *data for policy* and *design for policy*. Both fields systematically analyse and experiment with innovative practices in policy-making. Also, both fields aim to introduce new sources of insights and nurture broader innovation in governmental organisations. Although the two fields appear far in many senses, room for cross-fertilisation can be seen by looking at practitioners' experimentations. Therefore, this article asks the following question: it is possible to imagine newly emerging areas of convergence between *data for policy* and *design for policy*? To answer, one should first define innovation in a way that can adapt to both.

1 The framework of public sector innovation

In the last years, several events¹ testify the political interest increasingly surrounding Public Sector Innovation (from now on PSI). In 2013, the European Commission appointed a milestone report² on PSI to an international group of experts. In the same year, the OECD Public Governance Committee established the Observatory of Public Sector Innovation (OPSI) to foster and advocate PSI among the OECD's member states (OECD, 2015). OPSI's efforts throughout the years led to increased political awareness and culture regarding PSI. For example, forty national governments recently signed an international agreement on the pivotal role of PSI and the general principles for its support (OECD, 2019). This commitment to PSI translated into an emerging global movement of policy-makers and public servants (Bason, 2010, pp. 4–5). PSI's conceptual roots are ancient, datable to the writings of Alexis de Tocqueville and Max Weber (Kattel et al., 2018). As a concept, it recently gained popularity while remaining largely undefined (Pollitt, 2011). There are three main arguments usually indicated to explain the current interest in PSI. First, the weight of the public sector within national economies. In fact, “*in high-income countries the public sector contributes to between 20% and 30% of GDP*” (Arundel et al., 2019, p. 789). Adopting innovation could make a relevant difference in this sector and overall states' economies, whereas its lack might lead to stagnation and waste. The need to ensure efficiency through the continuous rethink of governmental functions — particularly in times of financial crisis — is certainly not new (see Osborne & Gaebler, 1992; Roessner, 1977). In particular, the efficiency-focused paradigm of PSI was strong during the 80s, when public administrators, influenced by the New Public Management (NPM) theories, emulated management and governance models (e.g., decentralisation) from the private sector (Hartley, 2005; Thenint, 2010). A second argument that motivates interest in PSI is the widely accepted idea that we live in a time of *wicked problems* (Rittel & Webber, 1973). The term was conceived to describe the inherent complexity of societal challenges while at the same time outlining the limits of the government's traditional problem-solving approach. Hence, PSI is considered an essential element to enable governments' adaption to the highly complex challenges of our times (Ansell & Torfing, 2014; Bason, 2010; Kattel et al., 2014). Lastly, a third key argument regards the changing relationship between citizens and governments, which closely connects with the critical role public services plays in our societies. Unlike innovation in the private sector, which traditionally focused on product development and new technology adoption (Borins, 2001; Lorena et al., 2012), PSI “*is usually not a physical artefact*

[...] but a change in the relationships between service providers and their users.” (Hartley, 2005, p. 27).

Citizens should be no longer considered customers but rather co-producers of public services (Hartley, 2005). This perspective gained ground as the tertiary sector boomed during the last years, and new theories of value — notably the Service-Dominant logic (Lusch & Vargo, 2006) — emphasised the service suppliers/users interaction as the hub of value creation. In the public sphere, Elinor Ostrom (1996) outlined the pivotal role of citizens' inputs in supporting public infrastructures and services. For all these reasons, the need to rethink governance structures underlies PSI. The co-creation/co-production paradigm would then become, for PSI, a characterising element, a driver and a desirable goal at the same time (Bason, 2010; Bekkers & Tummers, 2018; Selloni, 2017). Moreover, the will of addressing citizens' needs and expectations further sustains PSI (Mulgan & Albury, 2003, p. 2). Given these three points, we can better contextualise today's primary definition of PSI: the ideation and implementation of “*new ideas that create value for society*” (Bason, 2010, p. 4). Here we found the concept of public value (Moore, 1995), which maintains that public managers should bring value to society, as private managers bring value to their companies (Moore, 1995, p. 28). *Public value* is a compelling concept that can synergise the work of many governmental actors striving for the same goals, e.g., public managers and policy designer (Mintrom & Luetjens, 2017). Nonetheless, defining value in the private sector is relatively easy (i.e., revenue), whilst how to identify and measure public value — and consequently PSI — is still debated (Bloch & Bugge, 2013; De Vries et al., 2016; Kattel et al., 2018; Pollitt, 2011). Accordingly, recent studies have focused on what makes PSI different from private sector innovation (Lember et al., 2018). Perhaps as part of this distancing, scholars have outlined several subcategories of PSI (see Hartley, 2005; Windrum, 2008). For example, governance innovation, conceptual innovation, service innovation. All these subsets are traditionally neglected topic within innovation studies (Windrum, 2008). Among them, we can also find *policy innovation*.

2 Policy innovation as innovative ways of learning

In the literature dealing with PSI, one can find different definitions of policy innovation. For example: “*new policy directions and initiatives*” (Mulgan & Albury, 2003, p. 4); “*a specific kind of innovation that involves the formulation, implementation and diffusion of new visions of what a good society is, concrete goals inspired by these visions, and strategies for moving society in the desired direction*” (Agger & Sørensen, 2014, p. 189); or even “*the change of*

¹ For a more exhaustive list of worldwide governmental initiatives for PSI support, see Bason (2010).

² See EC (2013).

values and knowledge in a policy network” (Windrum, 2008, p. 10). In particular, Windrum elaborated further on the dynamics of policy innovation by connecting it to different types of learning and outcomes. For example, learning about the actual effectiveness of policy tools would lead to incremental innovations by adjusting these same tools. Instead, when subjects in a policy network reconsider their shared understanding of policy problems and solutions, this type of learning might result in more radical forms of conceptual innovation.

Moreover, when the subjects involved in policy-making critically rethink their current social interactions and roles, they undergo social learning that might reshape the existing governance structures. Windrum had drawn on earlier studies of scholars in political and policy sciences by linking policy innovation and learning (Sabatier, 1987). He also recognised that this research strand “*fails to address innovation*”, as it only considered “policy change” and “reform” (Windrum, 2008, p. 3). Political science and policy studies traditionally regarded “*policy innovation*” not as the invention of original policies but as the first adoption of policies and programs in a context where they did not exist before (even if these existed in other political systems) (Berry & Berry, 1990; Mintrom, 1997).

On another level, the same literature considers “*policy change*” (i.e., the modifications of policies during the time) as incremental innovation (Bennett & Howlett, 1992). By investigating causes and agents of policy innovation and change, scholars deemed *policy learning* (i.e. “*the updating of beliefs based on lived or witnessed experiences, analysis or social interaction*” (Dunlop & Radaelli, 2012, p. 599)) as an essential driver for both. While literature suggests that policy learning is a significant factor explaining policy innovation/change, a clear causal connection is never presented as obvious (Bennett & Howlett, 1992). Although learning takes place in a policy network, innovation at the level of core beliefs (what Windrum would call “*conceptual innovation*”) might be provoked by factors that are exogenous³ to the learning network (e.g., a national emergency). In my opinion, the link between policy innovation and learning offers an interesting vantage point for shifting the traditional focus from *policy innovation conceived as new outputs* (i.e., new policies adopted) toward *innovation conceived as new processes for policy* (cf. Vaz & Prendeville, 2019). In other words, I propose to see policy innovation as *the application of innovative means through which policy actors learn about policy problems*. This type of learning might ultimately affect how these actors conceptualise policy issues, values and goals and, in turn, how policies are designed.

³ This is, for example, Sabatier’s perspective (1987) on policy-oriented learning.

3 Data for policy and design for policy: where do they stand?

The perspective on policy innovation here proposed is certainly debatable. As the literature in policy studies warns us, learning is just among the elements that might cause innovation and change in policy (Berry & Berry, 2018). New policies often result from imitating what worked in other contexts and without relation to design. Nonetheless, the multi-layered phenomenon of policy learning, spanning from the micro to the macro-level (Dunlop & Radaelli, 2017), functions well with the notion of policy innovation as a process (Vaz & Prendeville, 2019). Learning dynamics can explain innovation dynamics or, in other words, why new solutions at the micro-level (i.e., policy work and practices) influence the macro-level. This perspective seems valuable when looking at the *data for policy* and *design for policy* purposes and to imagine a potential integration between them. By zooming out from data analytics or design thinking in policy settings as innovation in themselves, a learning-focused inquiry would ask what type of learning these innovative practices entail, how this learning affects the various policy levels and whether this is innovative or not. In light of learning, we could ask if novel approaches and technologies enable innovative policy design spaces (Chindarkar et al., 2017). In line with this perspective, I propose the areas of convergence between *data for policy* and *design for policy*. Before doing so, I will briefly present both.

3.1 Data for policy

Data for policy investigates the intersection between the use of digital data and policy-making. The community working in this field is interested in several topics: the potential of leveraging data sources traditionally not used in policy-making (e.g., Internet data); new organisational settings and collaborations designed to share these data (e.g., data collaboratives); related techniques and technologies for analysis (e.g., network analysis, Machine Learning); critical issues related to data quality, privacy and epistemology when non-traditional data are used for public decision-making. The use of non-traditional data sources seems to offer an unprecedented potential to analyse patterns of behaviours within large scale systems, e.g. cities (Bettencourt, 2014). These data⁴ might enhance the analytical capacity of policy-makers, allowing analysis of large scale issues in real-time (Hemerly, 2013; Maciejewski, 2017; Mureddu et al., 2012) or through forecasting (Athey, 2017). There is general agreement that data will increasingly impact policy-making (Giest, 2017), but little empirical evidence exists connecting data and policy (Poel et al., 2018; Verhulst et al., 2019).

⁴ E.g., data integrated among public departments, coming from the private sector or collected from non-traditional sources (e.g., citizen-generated).

3.2 Design for policy

The relation between design and policy originates in the orientation of design discipline toward complex systems (Buchanan, 1992; Jones, 2015) and the social sphere (Hillgren et al., 2011; Markussen, 2017).

Design for policy practically manifested through a growing number of cases in which design approaches, methods, and tools related to service design were adopted within governments (Bason & Schneider, 2014; Kimbell, 2015). This adoption mainly happened within public sector innovation labs, i.e., special groups or units entitled by governments with a variegated agenda for supporting PSI (Tönurist et al., 2017). It must be noted that *design for policy* presents substantial differences from traditional policy design (Clarke & Craft, 2019; Mortati, 2019). Policy design is considered a specific type of policy formulation in which new policy goals are defined based on available knowledge on the effects of policy tools (Howlett, 2019). It developed as a rather technocratic and mechanistic inquiry on the effectiveness of policy tools, their interaction in policy mixes and the political and government capacities for design to happen (Peters et al., 2018). Instead, *design for policy* focuses on heuristics, creativity and abduction logic to public problem solving (Considine, 2012). By adopting a human-centred approach (i.e., investigating beneficiaries' experience) to policies and public services development, *design for policy* seeks to productively reduce the gap between design and implementation (Christiansen & Bunt, 2014; Junginger, 2013). Within design for policy, policy workers inductively collect insights from stakeholders to incorporate them into the final design of policies and services (Hermus et al., 2020). Consequently, this approach often concretely translates into participatory settings in which visualisations and prototyping techniques are employed to prefigure future solutions (e.g., services) and engage with stakeholders (Bason, 2017; Kimbell, 2015; Kimbell & Bailey, 2017). Design for policy has been criticised for being naïve to political/governance structures, hardly scalable and uncritical in privileging only a networked policy style (Clarke & Craft, 2019; Howlett, 2020).

4 Design for policy in data for policy practices: potential areas of convergence

Innovating how governments learn about policy issues (and consequently improving policy implementation and public services design) stands as a proposition both in *data for policy* and *design for policy*. Both fields seek to experiment with innovative approaches, methods and tools

to understand public issues and orient governmental interventions. In the perspective of this paper, the main difference between the two resides in a different epistemological approach when it comes to investigating policy problems. If *design for policy* privileges observational and inductive investigations that gather knowledge by probing users' needs and expectations, the *data for policy* approach implies understanding policy-related phenomena by "letting the data speak for themselves" (Bettencourt, 2014; Kitchin, 2014). Despite this theoretical distance, examples of cross-fertilisation between these fields seem to be emerging in several experiments. For example, the Policy Lab in UK Government Cabinet Office, a notable subject in *design for policy* landscape, used big data and "thick" data (from ethnographic research) to support a human-centred approach to policy-making (Siodmok, 2020). On the other hand, relevant subjects advocating data-driven innovation, e.g., The United Nations Pulse Lab Jakarta, explicitly used service design methods and tools in their portfolio (Pulse Lab Jakarta, 2019). Although, a theoretical perspective that connects policy, design and data is still missing⁵ (Mortati, 2019). Empirical research on the adoption of design in public management could not find much on the use of data (Bason, 2017). Public sector innovation labs adopted design and human-centred methods but primarily focused on ICT, digital governance, and open data rather than data science (see Tönurist et al., 2017; see Williamson, 2015 for a different perspective). I address this gap as a doctoral student in design by looking at the *data for policy* field. I analysed the proceedings of the previous editions of the "*Data for Policy*" Conference (2015, 2016, 2017, 2019) available on Zenodo. This body of literature arguably constitutes a relevant representative sample of the *data for policy* discourse, while it cannot be held as totally representative for this whole evolving field. The proceedings included 74 papers that I reviewed by assigning codes with qualitative analysis software. I developed my coding in order to identify examples relatable to *design for policy*. As expected, reasonable ground for proposing convergences could only be found in few articles. These articles often explicitly addressed topics as participatory approaches in data governance, co-creation, citizens empowerment and data literacy. They included theoretical discussions (e.g., on data sharing models) and/or cases study presentation. As only scattered elements eventually emerged from coding, I could not recognise patterns throughout the articles. Although, the analysis outlined punctual cases that could work as illustrative examples to support the areas of convergence here proposed. I articulated these areas accordingly to the perspective on learning explained above.

⁵ An example of research on integrating design thinking and data science for public purposes has been developed by the Innovation Insight Hub of

4.1 Area of Convergence: Learning from Data-driven Anticipatory Governance

This area of convergence starts from an old idea: governments should develop policies by anticipating futures events (Osborne & Gaebler, 1992). Today many governments actively engage with the systematic prefiguration of possible future scenarios to approach strategy-making and adapt to unpredictable events. This activity is usually operationalised through foresight methods and techniques. By applying elements from the design practice, the disciplinary design field developed a specific approach to prefiguration (namely *designing futures*). *Designing futures* employs diegetic prototypes and visualisations to build normative and contextual visions in participatory settings (e.g., imagining possible future services or governance settings) (Wilkinson, 2017). Kimbell (2019) connects this practice to the *design for policy* field. She offers several examples of how the two can complement to enable new spaces, which she called “studios”, devoted to handling policy complexity and uncertainty and collectively analysing past data and existing evidence.

Studios enable people to make problems graspable and imaginable in the face of high levels of ambiguity, complexity and uncertainty. They translate between local, digital and expert knowledge and data and bring into view their different grounding myths, discourses and framings. (Kimbell, 2019, p. 134)

In the view of *data for policy*, this approach can probe the publics’ opinion during data technologies development. For example, Jacobs et al. (2019) used diegetic prototypes to understand public acceptance of IoT technologies deployment, consequently identifying governance, transparency and accountability issues. These activities are not only relevant for consultation but can define pivotal questions affecting the design of these systems:

It is important to ask such questions at the start of the process and as data are being collected, and consider why data needs to be collected at all, rather than just collecting it because it is there with usefulness to be decided later. (Jacobs et al., 2019, p. 5)

Predicting futures is also one of the major promises of data within the *data for policy* field, as mathematical modelling allows simulation of systems’ future behaviours (i.e., forecasting). Forecasting tools might be enriched by integrating existing quantitative data and by collecting, through stakeholders involvement, new qualitative data from specific contexts. Dutt et al. (2019) described the development of a scenario-based simulation platform called “*Simulogue*”, experimented in the administrative region of Chennai, India. The platform integrates

quantitative data (e.g., registry on land-use) and qualitative data (e.g., report on the interaction between stakeholders) to improve policy decision-making, enabling dialogue and reflection on futures strategies. Data-driven anticipatory governance can be a context in which insights from a participated conversation on futures mixes with data-driven probabilistic predictions (see Maffei et al., 2020).

4.2 Area of Convergence: Learning from local/contextual knowledge

The inclusion of contextual/local knowledge is an essential trait of *design for policy*. This type of knowledge can be valuable in supporting a descriptive/diagnostic analysis of data within policy-oriented data activities. In other words, local/contextual knowledge is a way through which we can identify causal mechanisms underlying patterns emerging from data analysis. To give a concrete example, we can consider the promising field of Positive Deviance based on “big data”. In itself, the Positive Deviance approach (often used in social development intervention) seeks to individuate individuals or communities performing exceptionally well compared to peers to replicate what makes them successful and achieve policy goals. In this case, big data analysis can help to identify these outliers, but the reasons underlying their outstanding performances can only be discovered by engaging and observing these contexts closely (Stermin et al., 2019). On a more sophisticated level, the inclusion of local/contextual knowledge in *data for policy* can lead to reconsidering and shaping data ontologies (i.e., the organisation of concepts and relationships representing the domain quantified through data). Edwards et al. (2017) showcased a participatory format, called *Data Walk*, for reshaping data ontologies by incorporating local knowledge.

The interdisciplinary team Ensemble developed the *Data Walk* with the two-fold aim of collecting data on flooding while engaging communities in critically reflecting about what was worth measuring for addressing that issue. The aim was to foster the interplay between experts and laypersons knowledge, thus reconsidering the data ontologies upon which the flood detection information system was based. This integrative method may affect the whole epistemology of data-driven policy design concerning complex issues:

The advantage of using semantic integration in the construction of a scenario library goes beyond the ability to interrogate data from different perspectives. It also allows for the incorporation of novel data, qualitative data and localised data with existing data sources to present richer, nuanced picture of places with the potential for more refined models of risk and uncertainty. (Edwards et al., 2017, p. 3)

4.2 Area of Convergence: *Learning from Services Systems*.

Digitalised services are a valuable source of *data for policy*. Data might be collected through digital public-owned services and by accessing private-owned service systems that continuously collect data to ensure their standards (e.g., multi-utility companies). It is unlikely that all data related to a complex policy-relevant phenomenon resides within a unique service system. A holistic view of existing services systems would allow a wise combination of separated information systems into a unique one.

A careful integration could start from mapping the service journey of subjects that the policy will affect. In the words of Ubaldi et. Al (2019):

Data analytics enable a closer working relationship between policy design and service delivery activities with a resulting shift from top-down implementation of public services to a user need led approach to design and delivery, based on an end to end understanding of a particular service journey, which can consequently increase its reach and effectiveness. (Ubaldi et al., 2019, p. 22)

The inquiry into service systems to gather and integrate data for policy design could become an innovative practice of policy learning. A perspective on service design and services end-users, which is central in the *design for policy* approach, will be needed to find the necessary and sufficient service data to assess policy problems. Malomo and Sena (2017) offer an illustrative example in this sense by describing the case of an integrated data model for Kent County Council Children's Service (UK). Data from the different county's services were integrated into a model that could give a novel view about children's behaviours and how they used these services. This service data (e.g., public libraries underutilisation) can, on the one hand, led to the adjustment of single services (e.g., closing libraries to cut expenses). However, they can also provide insights useful for policy purposes (e.g., acknowledging and addressing young people's lack of interest in reading). In brief, the mutual reinforcement of *design* and *data for policy* in learning from service systems could be two-fold. On the one hand, the *design for policy* approach provides exploratory methods and techniques to map services journey starting from their users, thus allowing the integration of those data sources relevant to understanding a policy-relevant phenomenon (for example, as in the example above, young people behaviours). On the other hand, given that services are, in many policy domains, resultants of policy implementation, if implementers consider the *data for policy* perspective during service design, the resulting service systems can become a valuable way to monitor and evaluate policies *by design*⁶.

⁶ See, as an example, the initiative of "Their Future Matters" (New South Wales Government, Australia), which developed a forecasting model based on service and administrative data (Taylor Fry, 2019).

Discussion

Non-traditional data and data analytics seem to represent a disruptive factor in policy-making, but technology may be reductive in the delicate policy domains where the issues addressed are highly complex. While specialised knowledge is essential for public sector innovation, disciplinary silos and closed epistemic communities might diminish our capacity to reckon the lacks in each innovative field. As both *data* and *design for policy* are novel, the current moment might be the right one to ask if and how these fields should join, ultimately considering the current public sector and policy innovation goals.

The convergences I proposed attempted to articulate an answer in this sense by thinking of policy innovation as *innovative processes* that contribute to enhanced policy-making. *Data and design for policy seem well suited to work together by enabling innovative ways of policy learning*, which is a relevant factor in policy innovation. I employed illustrative examples found in the *data for policy* field to support the proposed areas of convergence. However, this effort is undoubtedly insufficient to develop a robust methodological model or framework for practice. Hence, the conceptualisation of this convergence should in the future couple with more empirical evidence of how these practices concretely unfold in the public sector. Nevertheless, the argument presented is hopefully worth considering by those attempting to understand how we can shape new epistemologies of policy-making, especially in those policy domains characterised by complex policy goals (e.g., circular economy policies, social policies).

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References

- Agger, A., & Sørensen, E. (2014). Designing collaborative policy innovation: Lessons from a Danish municipality. In C. Ansell, & J. Torfing. (Eds.). *Public Innovation Through Collaboration and Design*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203795958>

- Ansell, C., & Torfing, J. (Eds.). (2014). Public innovation through collaboration and design. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203795958>
- Arundel, A., Bloch, C., & Ferguson, B. (2019). Advancing innovation in the public sector: Aligning innovation measurement with policy goals. *Research Policy*, 48(3), 789–798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.12.001>
- Athey, S. (2017). Beyond prediction: Using big data for policy problems. *Science*, 355(6324), 483–485. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal4321>
- Bason, C. (2010). *Leading public sector innovation: Co-creating for a better society*. Policy Press. <https://doi.org/10.1332/policypress/9781847426345.001.0001>
- Bason, C. (2017). *Leading Public Design: How Managers Engage with Design to Transform Public Governance*. Copenhagen Business School [Phd]. PhD series, No. 21.
- Bason, C., & Schneider, A. (2014). Public Design in Global Perspective: Empirical Trends. In C. Bason (Ed.), *Design for Policy* (pp. 23–40). Gower Publishing.
- Bekkers, V., & Tummers, L. (2018). Innovation in the public sector: Towards an open and collaborative approach. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 84(2), 209–213. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852318761797>
- Bennett, C. J., & Howlett, M. (1992). The lessons of learning: Reconciling theories of policy learning and policy change. *Policy Sciences*, 25, 275–294. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00138786>
- Berry, F. S., & Berry, W. D. (1990). State Lottery Adoptions as Policy Innovations: An Event History Analysis. *American Political Science Review*, 84(2). <https://doi.org/10.2307/1963526>
- Berry, F. S., & Berry, W. D. (2018). Innovation and Diffusion Models in Policy Research. In C. M. Weible & P. A. Sabatier (Eds.), *Theories of the Policy Process*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429494284-8>
- Bettencourt, L. M. A. (2014). The uses of big data in cities. *Big Data*, 2(1), 12–22. <https://doi.org/10.1089/big.2013.0042>
- Bloch, C., & Bugge, M. M. (2013). Public sector innovation - From theory to measurement. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, 27, 133–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.strueco.2013.06.008>
- Borins, S. (2001). Encouraging innovation in the public sector. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 2(3), 310–319. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14691930110400128>
- Buchanan, R. (1992). Wicked Problems in Design Thinking. *Design Issues*, 8(2), 5–21. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1511637>
- Chindarkar, N., Howlett, M., & Ramesh, M. (2017). Introduction to the Special Issue: “Conceptualizing Effective Social Policy Design: Design Spaces and Capacity Challenges.” *Public Administration and Development*, 37(1), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pad.1789>
- Christiansen, J., & Bunt, L. (2014). Innovating Public Policy: Allowing for Social Complexity and Uncertainty in the Design of Public Outcomes. In C. Bason (Ed.), *Design for Policy* (pp. 41–56). Gower Publishing.
- Clarke, A., & Craft, J. (2019). The twin faces of public sector design. *Governance*, 32(1), 5–21. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gove.12342>
- Considine, M. (2012). Thinking Outside the Box? Applying Design Theory to Public Policy. *Politics and Policy*, 40(4), 704–724. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-1346.2012.00372.x>
- De Vries, H., Bekkers, V., & Tummers, L. (2016). Innovation in the public sector: A systematic review and future research agenda. *Public Administration*, 94(1), 146–166. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12209>
- Dunlop, C. A., & Radaelli, C. M. (2012). Systematising Policy Learning: From Monolith to Dimensions. *Political Studies*, 61(3), 599–619. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9248.2012.00982.x>
- Dunlop, C. A., & Radaelli, C. M. (2017). Learning in the bath-tub: The micro and macro dimensions of the causal relationship between learning and policy change. *Policy and Society*, 36(2), 304–319. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14494035.2017.1321232>
- Dutt, V., Sil, S., Krishna, H., & Palavalli, B. (2019). *Imagining Futures – A generative scenario-based methodology to improve planning and decision-support systems for policymakers*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3066348>
- Edwards, L., Mullagh, L., Towe, R., Nundloll, V., Dean, C., Dean, G., Simm, W., Samreen, F., Bassett, R., Blair, G. (2017, September 4). *Data-driven decisions for flood risk management*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.884180>
- European Commission. (2013). *Powering European Public Sector Innovation: Towards a New Architecture*. Report of the Expert Group on Public Sector Innovation. https://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/pdf/psi_eg.pdf
- Giest, S. (2017). Big data for policymaking: fad or fasttrack? *Policy Sciences*, 50(3), 367–382. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-017-9293-1>
- Hartley, J. (2005). Innovation in governance and public services: Past and present. *Public Money and Management*, 25(1), 27–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9302.2005.00447.x>
- Hemerly, J. (2013). Public policy considerations for data-driven innovation. *Computer*, 46(6), 25–31. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2013.186>

- Hermus, M., van Buuren, A., & Bekkers, V. (2020). Applying design in public administration: A literature review to explore the state of the art. *Policy and Politics*, 48(1), 21–48. <https://doi.org/10.1332/030557319X15579230420126>
- Hillgren, P. A., Seravalli, A., & Emilson, A. (2011). Prototyping and infrastructuring in design for social innovation. *CoDesign*, 7(3–4), 169–183. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15710882.2011.630474>
- Howlett, M. (2019). *Designing Public Policies. Principles and Instruments*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315232003>
- Howlett, M. (2020). Challenges in applying design thinking to public policy: Dealing with the varieties of policy formulation and their vicissitudes. *Policy and Politics*, 48(1), 49–65. <https://doi.org/10.1332/030557319X15613699681219>
- Jacobs, N., Edwards, P., Markovic, M., Cottrill, C. D., & Salt, K. (2019). *Public Sector Internet of Things Deployments: Value, Transparency, Risks and Challenges*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2713118>
- Jenson, J. (2015). Social Innovation: Redesigning the Welfare Diamond. In: Nicholls A., Simon J., Gabriel M. (eds) *New Frontiers in Social Innovation Research*. Palgrave Macmillan, London. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137506801_5
- Jones, P. H. (2015). Systemic Design Principles for Complex Social Systems. In G. S. Metcalf (Ed.), *Social Systems and Design* (Translatio, Vol. 1, pp. 91–128). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-4-431-54478-4>
- Junginger, S. (2013). Design and Innovation in the Public Sector: Matters of Design in Policy-Making and Policy Implementation. *Annual Review of Policy Design*, 1(1), 1–11. <http://ojs.unbc.ca/index.php/design/article/view/542>
- Kattel, R., Cepilovs, A., Drechsler, W., Kalvet, T., Lember, V., & Tõnurist, P. (2014). Can we measure public sector innovation? A literature review. In *LIPSE Working papers* (Issue 2).
- Kattel, R., Cepilovs, A., Lember, V., & Tõnurist, P. (2018). Indicators for public sector innovations: Theoretical frameworks and practical applications. *Halduskultuur*, 19(1), 77–104. <https://doi.org/10.32994/ac.v19i1.208>
- Kimbell, Lucy (2015) Applying Design Approaches to Policy Making: Discovering Policy Lab. Discussion Paper. University of Brighton, Brighton.
- Kimbell, L. (2019). What If There Were More Policy Futures Studios? *Journal of Future Studies*, 23(4), 129–136. [https://doi.org/10.6531/JFS.201906_23\(4\).0014](https://doi.org/10.6531/JFS.201906_23(4).0014)
- Kimbell, L., & Bailey, J. (2017). Prototyping and the new spirit of policy-making. *CoDesign*, 13(3), 214–226. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15710882.2017.1355003>
- Kitchin, R. (2014). Big Data, new epistemologies and paradigm shifts. *Big Data and Society*, 1(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951714528481>
- Lember, V., Kattel, R., & Tõnurist, P. (2018). Technological capacity in the public sector: the case of Estonia. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 84(2), 214–230. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852317735164>
- Lorena, R. L., Simmonds, P., & Roma, L. (2012). Trends and challenges in public sector innovation in Europe. December, 1–56. published by DG Enterprise, Brussels.
- Lusch, R. F., & Vargo, S. L. (2006). Service-dominant logic: Reactions, reflections and refinements. *Marketing Theory*, 6(3), 281–288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1470593106066781>
- Maciejewski, M. 2017. To Do More, Better, Faster and More Cheaply: Using Big Data in Public Administration. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 83(1_suppl), 120–135. doi:10.1177/0020852316640058
- Maffei, S., Leoni, F., & Villari, B. (2020). Data-driven Anticipatory Governance. Emerging scenarios in data for policy practices. In L., Kimbell & L., Vesnic-Alujevic (Eds.) *The Future of Government: Exploring Futures through Design and Foresight* [Special issue]. *Policy Design and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2020.1763896>
- Malomo, F., & Sena, V. (2017). Data Intelligence for Local Government? Assessing the Benefits and Barriers to Use of Big Data in the Public Sector. *Policy and Internet*, 9(1), 7–27. <https://doi.org/10.1002/poi3.141>
- Markussen, T. (2017). Disentangling ‘the social’ in social design’s engagement with the public realm. *CoDesign*, 13(3), 160–174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15710882.2017.1355001>
- Mintrom, M. (1997). Policy Entrepreneurs and the Diffusion of Innovation. *American Journal of Political Science*. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2111674>
- Mintrom, M., & Luetjens, J. (2017). Creating Public Value: Tightening Connections Between Policy Design and Public Management. *Policy Studies Journal*, 45(1), 170–190. <https://doi.org/10.1111/psj.12116>
- Moore, M. H. (1995). *Creating public value: Strategic management in government*. Harvard university press.
- Mortati, M. (2019). The Nexus between Design and Policy: Strong, Weak, and Non-Design Spaces in Policy Formulation. *Design Journal*, 22(6), 775–792. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14606925.2019.1651599>
- Mulgan, G., & Albury, D. (2003). Innovation in the public sector. Strategy Unit, Cabinet Office, 1(1), 40.
- Mureddu, F., D. Osimo, G. Misuraca, and S. Armenia. 2012. A New Roadmap for Next-Generation Policy-

- Making. ICEGOV '12: Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance, 62–66.
[doi:10.1145/2463728.2463743](https://doi.org/10.1145/2463728.2463743)
- OECD. (2015). *The Innovation Imperative in the Public Sector: Setting an Agenda for Action*.
<https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264236561-en>
- OECD. (2019). *Declaration on Public Sector Innovation*. OECD/LEGAL/0450.<https://oecd-opsi.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/OECD-Declaration-on-Public-Sector-Innovation-English.pdf>
- Osborne, D., and T. Gaebler. 1992. *Reinventing Government*. New York: Addison-Wesley.
- Ostrom, E. (1996). Crossing the great divide: Coproduction, synergy, and development. *World Development*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X\(96\)00023-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X(96)00023-X)
- Peters, B. G., Capano, G., Howlett, M., Mukherjee, I., Chou, M.-H., & Ravinet, P. (2018). *Designing for Policy Effectiveness*. Cambridge University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108555081>
- Pulse Lab Jakarta. (2019, Nov). *Repositioning Pulse Lab Jakarta*. Medium. <https://medium.com/pulse-lab-jakarta/repositioning-pulse-lab-jakarta-ce66fca4d48f>
- Poel, M., Meyer, E. T., & Schroeder, R. (2018). Big Data for Policymaking: Great Expectations, but with Limited Progress? *Policy and Internet*, 10(3), 347–367.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/poi3.176>
- Pollitt, C. (2011). Innovation in the Public Sector: An Introductory Overview. In B. Bekkers, V. Edelenbos & J. Steijn (Eds.), *Innovation in the Public Sector* (pp. 35–43). Palgrave Macmillan.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429047879-1>
- Rittel, H. W. J., & Webber, M. M. (1973). Dilemmas in a general theory of planning. *Policy Sciences*, 4, 155–169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01405730>
- Roessner, J. D. (1977). Incentives to innovate in public and private organizations. *Administration & Society*, 9(3), 341–365.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/009539977700900304>
- Sabatier, P. (1987). Knowledge, Policy-Oriented Learning, and Policy Change. *Knowledge*, 8(4), 649–692.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0164025987008004005>
- Selloni, D. (2017). New Forms of Welfare: Relational Welfare, Second Welfare, Co-production. In *CoDesign for Public-Interest Services* (pp. 27–36). Springer.
- Siodmok, A. (2020, Jan) *Lab Long Read: Human-centred policy? Blending 'big data' and 'thick data' in national policy*. Policy Lab. UK Government Cabinet Office.
<https://openpolicy.blog.gov.uk/2020/01/17/lab-long-read-human-centred-policy-blending-big-data-and-thick-data-in-national-policy/>
- Sternin, M., Zanetti, C., & Thuesen, L. (2019, Jan). *How can Positive Deviance and Big Data be a set up for a Date?* Medium. <https://medium.com/@dppd/how-can-positive-deviance-and-big-data-be-a-set-up-for-a-date-cbb297267002>
- Taylor Fry. (2019). *Forecasting Future Outcomes. Stronger Communities Investment Unit — 2018 Insights Report*. New South Wales Government.
https://www.theirfuturesmatter.nsw.gov.au/_data/asset/s/pdf_file/0003/673284/Forecasting-Future-Outcomes-Stronger-Communities-Investment-U
- Thenint, H. (2010). *Mini Study 10 Innovation in the public sector*. Global Review of Innovation Intelligence and Policy Studies, 1-51.
- Tönurist, P., Kattel, R., & Lember, V. (2017). Innovation labs in the public sector: what they are and what they do? *Public Management Review*, 19(10), 1455–1479.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2017.1287939>
- Ubaldi, B., Van Ooijen, C., & Welby, B. (2019). *A data-driven public sector: Enabling the strategic use of data for productive, inclusive and trustworthy governance*. OECD Working Papers on Public Governance, 33, 1–59. <https://doi.org/10.1787/09ab162c-en>
- Vaz, F., & Prendeville, S. (2019). Design as an Agent for Public Policy Innovation. Conference Proceedings of the Academy for *Design Innovation Management*, 2(1).
<https://doi.org/10.33114/adim.2019.06.231>
- Verhulst, S. G., Engin, Z., & Crowcroft, J. (2019). Data & Policy: A new venue to study and explore policy–data interaction. *Data & Policy*, 1, 1–5.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/dap.2019.2>
- Wilkinson, A. 2017. *Strategic Foresight Primer*. European Political Strategy Centre.
https://cor.europa.eu/Documents/Migrated/Events/EPS_C_strategic_foresight_primer.pdf
- Williamson, B. (2015). Governing methods: Policy innovation labs, design and data science in the digital governance of education. *Journal of Educational Administration and History*, 47(3), 251–271.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00220620.2015.1038693>
- Windrum, P. (2008). Innovation and entrepreneurship in public services. In *Innovation in Public Sector Services: Entrepreneurship, Creativity and Management* (pp. 3–20).
<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781848441545.00009>